

Sustainable Apparel Purchase Intention: Influence of Branding on Indian Consumers

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Abstract:

Background: Sustainable apparel which combines ethical production with environmental responsibility, has become an integral part of the global fashion industry. This evolution reflects increasing consumer demand for products that reduce environmental harm while upholding social accountability. As the textile sector faces heightened scrutiny over its environmental footprint, sustainable apparel provides a pathway for aligning industry practices with global sustainability objectives. This study explores how branding influences consumer purchase intentions for sustainable apparel.

Method: An empirical study was conducted based on data gathered from 210 consumers in Delhi NCR who consistently buy sustainable apparel. SPSS 26 was used to do regression analysis.

Results: These results underscore the critical value of branding in shaping consumer choice and propelling eco-friendly purchasing behaviors. Focusing on branding, the article fills a gap in the current literature, where more research accounts for issues of cost and functionality vis-a-vis other concerns such as sustainability. The findings show that sustainable brands should invest in being perceived as authentic and trustworthy, to win loyalty. Effective communication and powerful sustainability stories are critical to align with changing consumer values.

Conclusion: This body of study offers new insights for businesses, marketers, and policymakers, underlining the integration of branding strategy with sustainability that targets responsible consumption and supports larger societal and environmental goals.

Keywords: *Branding, brand authenticity, brand reputation, purchase intention, sustainable apparel*

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1. Introduction

The apparel industry has greatly contributed to global environmental concerns and fast fashion has been the focus of all sustainability discussions. Consumers are becoming increasingly aware of their choices and their impact on the environment. Hence there is an influx of products that are sustainable and more environment-friendly. On the other hand, however, despite this growing awareness, traditional aspects like price, quality, style, and fit are still key influencers of most purchase decisions. It is a challenge for sustainable apparel brands to meet customer expectations on these conventional considerations [2, 11].

Branding has emerged as a key tool for influencing consumer behavior, particularly in sectors where differentiation is vital. A strong brand can foster trust, create emotional connections, and signal reliability and quality. This is especially important in the sustainable apparel market, where unfamiliarity with eco-friendly materials and processes can complicate purchasing decisions. Consumers often rely on brand cues, such as reputation and authenticity, to guide their choices, especially when a brand is perceived as a leader in

sustainability. Despite the growing interest in eco-friendly fashion, the influence of branding on purchase intentions for sustainable apparel remains underexplored. The influence of branding attributes on the purchase intention of sustainable products is underexplored and a smaller number of studies examined the branding variables in the sustainable category [4, 7, 8, 9].

This paper investigates the influence of branding factors such as brand strength, reputation, and authenticity on consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable apparel. It assists in understanding the drivers of sustainable shopping behavior. Knowledge of the role of branding in consumer choice is thus pertinent to the business community, as well as policymakers who wish to encourage more sustainable consumption. This study fills an important gap in existing literature by highlighting how branding can be a strategic tool to encourage sustainable fashion choices. Therefore, the three objectives of this study are:

RO1: To examine the influence of brand strength on consumer purchase intention for sustainable apparel.

RO2: To examine the influence of brand reputation on consumers' purchase intention for sustainable apparel.

RO3: To examine the influence of brand authenticity on consumer purchase intention for sustainable apparel.

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2. Review of Literature and Hypothesis Development

The increased pressure on the apparel industry to reduce its negative environmental and social impact highlights the importance of research in sustainable apparel. Prior work has focussed on the role of factors like cultural influence, price sensitivity, environmental concern, and perceived value in consumer decision-making. However, the aspect of branding in the context of sustainable apparel consumption remains largely unexplored. This literature gap thus calls for further research into the sustainability factors that influence consumer choice in the sustainable apparel and textile industry [1, 3, 5 & 10].

2.1 Brand Strength

Brand strength encompasses brand recognition, loyalty, trust, and perceived quality, which are important consumer behavior aspects. In the sustainable apparel and textile sector, brand strength has attracted considerable attention as consumers increasingly search for brands that satisfy their demands and underpin their green and ethical values. For example, the sustainable apparel brand 'Patagonia', is having high consumer loyalty due to consistently demonstrating leadership in environmental activism, high-quality outdoor clothing, and transparent supply chain practices. Having a unique brand identity based on sustainability can build trust and loyalty. Hence, it is hypothesized that:

H1: Brand strength significantly and positively influences consumer purchase intention for sustainable apparel.

2.2 Brand Reputation

Brand reputation is the overall perception related to the reliability and quality of the brand as well as whether it stands behind its values, including sustainability. Research indicates that consumers buy from a brand they view positively in terms of ethics and sustainable practices, where trust is a critical success factor for the marketplace. The brand openly shares details about its factories, production costs, and environmental impact. For example, the sustainable apparel brand 'Stella McCartney' is synonymous with high-end, sustainable fashion, earning a stellar reputation among both consumers and industry experts. The brand combines luxury with ethical practices, standing out in a market often criticized for unsustainable practices. The influence of brand reputation on sustainable apparel purchase intention underlines its relevance as a driving force of consumer behavior. Hence, it is hypothesized that:

H2: Brand reputation significantly and positively influences purchase intention for sustainable apparel.

2.3 Brand Authenticity

Brand authenticity is how authentic and transparent a brand is, about its values, more so in terms of sustainability. Authenticity can create trust and emotional engagement on the part of the consumer, especially when brands make some clear commitments toward sustainability. For example, the sustainable apparel brand 'Everlane' is celebrated for its

transparency and commitment to ethical manufacturing, and 'Anokha Bandhan' is having the green certifications embodying brand authenticity and emphasis on modern essentials made with sustainable materials like organic cotton and recycled polyester. In the sustainable apparel industry, authenticity is a tool for brands to differentiate and convince the consumer that the brand is serious about both environmental and social responsibility. Hence, it is hypothesized that:

H3: Brand authenticity significantly and positively influences consumer purchase intention for sustainable apparel.

Together, these hypotheses explore the pivotal role of branding in shaping sustainable consumer behavior, emphasizing how strength, reputation, and authenticity can drive the adoption of eco-conscious apparel. The conceptual model for the study based on the above hypothesis can be seen in Figure 1. The conceptual model demonstrates how different factors that influence sustainable apparel PI are connected. The figure displays how brand strength directly influences consumer purchasing behavior. Additionally, it shows that brand reputation and authenticity also influence the decision to buy. The model displays how important strategic branding elements encourage consumers in the apparel business to practice sustainable consumption.

Figure 1 – Conceptual Model (Source; Author's own elaboration)

3. Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative research design to investigate the influence of branding on consumers' purchase intentions toward sustainable apparel. A structured questionnaire was administered to gather data on key variables viz., brand strength, brand reputation, brand authenticity, and consumers' purchase intentions. The research approach enabled systematic exploration of the relationships between branding factors and sustainable apparel consumption, which are areas where literature is scarce.

3.1 Sample Profile

The proposed study targeted consumers in Delhi NCR who consistently buy sustainable apparel. Using convenient sampling procedure, 385 questionnaires were administered,

and 264 responses were received. Amongst the received responses, 210 were found to be valid for analysis. The demographic profile of respondents includes the age (21 years or more) and a filtering question of “do you know about sustainable apparel” was applied.

3.2 Data Collection Procedure

An offline surveying method was adopted to retrieve the data from the actual consumers of sustainable apparel. The questionnaire in the format of closed-ended and Likert-type scales was used to gather in-depth information on brand strength, reputation, and authenticity aspects. Before the actual distribution of the questionnaires, pretesting was done amongst a few consumers to check on clarity and reliability. Informed consent and confidentiality assurances were maintained throughout the process.

3.3 Measurement and Instrumentation

A structured questionnaire was used to collect the data. Brand reputation was measured based on quality, reliability, and credibility dimensions. Brand authenticity was measured basis of integrity, credibility, symbolism, and continuity and purchase intentions were measured basis the willingness of the consumers to buy sustainable apparel and their willingness to pay a premium. A 7-point Likert scale was used to capture the ratings. [6, 9]

3.4 Data Analysis

The data was analysed using SPSS version 26 to compute descriptive statistics viz. mean and standard deviation. Regression analysis was conducted to test the relationships amongst brand strength, reputation, authenticity and purchase intentions. This enabled us to find out the association, in terms of the significance and strength, between branding and consumers' purchase behavior.

4. Results and Discussion

The regression analysis results reveal significant findings regarding the influence of brand strength, reputation, and authenticity on consumers' purchase intention for sustainable apparel. Each of the three hypotheses is tested with the following key results.

4.1 Brand Strength and Purchase Intention

The regression analysis revealed that brand strength significantly influences consumers' purchase intention for sustainable apparel, explaining 15.8% of the variance. With a moderate positive correlation ($R = 0.397$), brand strength is a significant predictor of purchase intention ($p < 0.05$). The unstandardized coefficient of 0.379 suggests that for each unit increase in brand strength, consumer purchase intention increases by 0.379 units. The model fit is confirmed with a statistically significant F-value of 38.922 ($p < 0.05$), supporting H1. The model summary, ANOVA, and coefficients can be seen in the following tables (Table 1, 2, and 3).

Table 1 – Model summary table for brand strength

Model	R Square	Adjusted R Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
	0.158	0.154	397 ²	2.28976
Predictors: (Constant), Brand strength				

Table 2 – ANOVA table for brand strength

Model	Mean square	df	Sum of square	F	Sig.
Regression	204.068	1	204.068	38.922	.000 ^b
Residual	5.243	208	1090.547		
Total	1294.614	209	1294.614		
Dependent variable: Purchase intention for sustainable apparel					
Predictors: (constant), Brand strength					

Table 3 – Coefficients table for brand strength

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)					
Brand Strength	6.109	0.681		8.969	0
	0.379	0.061	0.397	6.239	0
Dependent Variable: Purchase intention for sustainable apparel					

4.2 Brand Reputation and Purchase Intention

Brand reputation has a stronger influence, explaining 27.6% of the variance in purchase intention. The R-value of 0.526 indicates a stronger positive correlation than brand strength. The unstandardized coefficient for brand reputation is 0.429, meaning a unit increase in brand reputation results in a 0.429-unit increase in purchase intention. The model fit is also statistically significant with an F-value of 79.476 ($p < 0.05$), confirming the importance of brand reputation in shaping sustainable apparel consumption. Thus, H2 is supported. The model summary, ANOVA, and coefficients can be seen in the following tables (Table 4, 5, and 6)

Table 4 – Model summary table for brand reputation

Model	R Square	Adjusted R Square	R	Std. error of the estimate
	0.276	0.273	.526 ^a	2..6317
Predictors: (Constant), Brand reputation				

Table 5 – ANOVA table for brand reputation

Model	Mean Square	df	Sum of Squares	F	Sig.
Regression	338.304	1	338.304	79.476	.000 ^b
Residual	4.257	208	885.391		
Total		209	1223.695		
Dependent Variable: Consumers' purchase intention					
Predictors: (Constant), brand reputation					

Table 6 - Coefficient table for brand reputation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	5.415	0.473		11.442	0
Brand reputation	0.429	0.048	0.526	8.915	

Dependent Variable: Consumers' purchase intention

4.3 Brand Authenticity and Purchase Intention

Brand authenticity, while important, explains a smaller portion of the variance (7.9%) compared to brand strength and reputation. The R-value of 0.280 indicates a positive correlation. The unstandardized coefficient for brand authenticity is 0.272, suggesting a moderate influence on purchase intention. The F-value of 17.760 ($p < 0.05$) indicates a statistically significant contribution to purchase intention. Although the influence is smaller, H3 is supported, highlighting that brand authenticity remains a significant factor. The model summary, ANOVA, and coefficients can be seen in the following tables (Table 7, 8, and 9).

Table 7 – Model summary table for brand authenticity

Model	R Square	Adjusted R square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
	0.079	0.074	.280 ^a	2.44027

Predictors: (Constant), brand authenticity

Table 8 – ANOVA table for brand authenticity

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	105.757	1	105.757	17.76	.000 ^b
Residual	1238.624	208	5.955		
Total	1344.381	209			

Dependent Variable: Consumers' purchase intention
Predictors: (Constant), brand authenticity

Table 9 – Coefficient table for brand authenticity

Model	Unstandardized coefficient		Unstandardized coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	8.138	0.656		12.409	0
Brand authenticity	0.272	0.065	0.28	4.214	0

Dependent Variable: Consumers' purchase intention

This research sheds light on the significant role that branding plays in influencing consumer decisions regarding sustainable apparel. The study reveals that elements such as brand strength, reputation, and authenticity are pivotal factors in shaping purchase intentions within this sector. Brand strength, which refers to aspects like brand recognition, loyalty, and trust, is found to positively influence

the purchase intention, though its influence is moderate. This supports prior studies suggesting that a strong brand identity fosters consumer trust and preference, particularly in sustainability-driven markets. Furthermore, the influence of brand reputation, which explained 27.6% of the variance in purchase intention, underscores the importance of consumer perceptions of a brand's reliability and ethical standing. Consumers gravitate toward brands with a strong reputation for ethical practices, enhancing the brand's ability to drive sustainable consumption. Brand authenticity is a strong dimension but is found to be slightly less influential compared to brand strength and reputation. This is consistent with studies that have established that authenticity influences consumer trust and emotional engagement, especially in cases where the brands are transparent about the green activities that they undertake. Consumers are attracted to brands that provide a personal type of value identification. It rings well with a person's sense of ethical alignment and social responsibility.

A key outcome of this study is that the importance of sustainability in branding should not be undermined. Sustainable apparel brands should work to establish stable, respectable, and legitimate brands to attract environmentally concerned consumers. Moreover, openness and communication regarding their efforts for sustainability are essential for building trust and promoting purchasing behavior in today's competitive fashion market. Further research can explore the association between branding and price or examine the influence of social media.

4.4 Implications

The results have key implications for business and policy. Sustainable apparel brands need to strengthen brand reputation and authenticity as they emerge as important purchase drivers by including authentic certifications (e.g., FSC, B Corp). Effective and transparent communication regarding their sustainability practices, ethical sourcing, and environmental responsibility will promote trust and loyalty amongst eco-conscious consumers. By focusing on building a strong brand that upholds values related to sustainability, sustainable apparel manufacturers can create long-term relationships with consumers. This implies that policymakers need to provide an environment that encourages sustainable apparel manufacturers so that it fosters more responsible consumer behaviour. Insights from this study can lead to the development of influential marketing strategies that address the growing environmental concerns amongst consumers.

4.5 Limitations and Future Research Directions

The study also has its limitations. Since the research sample is drawn from a single geographical region, based on convenience sampling, generalizations of findings to other markets may be limited. Moreover, further research should be conducted in different regions and represent a greater variety of demographic groups by taking a larger sample size. Future studies can also conduct a cross-cultural comparison

and the role of social media to understand the influence of branding attributes. This will enable the capturing of more in-depth sustainable apparel consumption patterns. Further, gaining an understanding of how branding is related to other influencing factors such as social media and pricing will help learn more about consumer purchase intention. Longitudinal studies on the long-term influence of sustainable apparel branding can also be conducted as future research. This study provides rich insights into how brand strength, reputation, and authenticity influence sustainable apparel consumption. It also has future research and practical implications for the dynamic sustainable apparel industry.

5. Conclusion

This study provides insights into the process of how branding

influences sustainable apparel purchase intention. Brands, by creating a trustworthy and positive brand image, would be able to foster consumer loyalty and ultimately enhance demand for sustainable apparel. Furthermore, the authenticity of a brand indicates that a brand effectively and openly communicates its sustainability practices to its consumers, to build consumer confidence. Useful insights have been garnered from this research, yet there is much room for further exploration. The purchase intention could be explored further based on attitude toward sustainability, product quality, and demographic differences. As sustainability becomes a growing concern for consumers, businesses need to change their branding practices so that they align with the emerging expectations of their target audience.

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